

Explore the Relationship Between Dental and ENT Conditions, Such as Temporomandibular Joint Disorders and Ear Pain

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Abstract

Background: Due to the anatomical proximity of the temporomandibular joint, muscles innervated by the trigeminal nerve, and ear structures, patients with any type of temporomandibular disorder (TMD) may experience a variety of symptoms in their temporomandibular joints, masticatory muscles, and associated structures. They may also experience otological symptoms, including otitis media, tinnitus, ear fullness, ear pain, hearing loss, hyperacusis, and vertigo.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to determine the frequency of ear problems reported in the medical records of 70 patients who were seen at the dental outpatient department of Saraswati Institute of Medical Sciences and ENT outpatient department at the Subharti Medical College, Uttar Pradesh.

Method: 70 medical records from patients of both sexes who were enrolled in the OPD records of both dental and ENT outpatient department over a two-year period were reviewed. Age, gender, and the existence of documented otologic symptoms were the variables examined. SPSS (IBM Statistic 20.0) was used to arrange and statistically analyze the data.

Results: A greater proportion of female patients between the ages of 41 and 50 were found. In 87% of TMD cases, otological symptoms (otitis media, tinnitus, deafness, dizziness, imbalance, and ear fullness) were present, irrespective of age or sex. The most common symptom was tinnitus (42%), which was followed by ear fullness (39%).

Conclusion: Even though they are not directly related to the ear, these findings confirm the link between TMJ problems and otological symptoms.

Keywords: Temporomandibular Joint, Tinnitus, Ear Ache, Temporomandibular Joint Disorders, Facial Pain, Dentistry.

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Introduction

The connection between the temporal bone and the jaw, known as the temporomandibular joint (TMJ), is divided by an articular disc [1]. The TMJ is necessary for the performance of jaw motions like laterality, propulsion, and mouth opening and closing. The performance of stomatognathic functions [2] depends on these motions. As a subclassification of musculoskeletal illnesses, temporomandibular disorders encompass a number of issues pertaining to the temporomandibular joint, related tissues, and the muscles of mastication [3]. These structures are involved in speech, breathing, swallowing, and chewing. Joint noises during mandibular movements, pain in the temporomandibular joint or surrounding it, changes in mandibular kinematics, deviations in mandibular opening and closing, and problems with laterality

and protrusion are all signs of temporomandibular disorders [4]. In their reviews of the literature on TMDs and their connection to auditory symptoms, Barreto et al. and Pita et al. came to the conclusion that there is a connection between the stomatognathic and auditory systems, which is also seen in the causes and effects of TMDs, ranging from hearing impairments to changes in the muscles and functions of the body [5,6].

Research has suggested that the anatomical closeness of the TMJ, trigeminal nerve-innervated muscles, and ear structures may contribute to the pathogenesis of otological complaints in TMD patients [7].

Furthermore, central or labyrinthine issues, such as Meniere's disease, vestibular function, visual, or

psychological disorders, benign tumors, otosclerosis, presbycusis, acoustic trauma, or noise-induced hearing loss, may be linked to the complaints of vertigo, tinnitus, and decreased auditory acuity. In addition to presenting audiological tests consistent with hearing loss, these circumstances may also be linked to other symptoms such as ear otitis media, fullness, hyperacusis, nausea, vomiting, and problems with focus and attention. ENT and hearing tests are typically within normal limits for these patients [8].

It is challenging to pinpoint a specific reason why ear problems occur in this population due to the multifactorial diversity that can produce TMDs [9]. According to epidemiological statistics, the prevalence of ear symptoms in the general population can range from 10% to 31%; however, in patients with TMD, this number rose to 85%, and 50% of patients were referred to otological concerns even if they did not initially present with ear problems [10,11]. Based on these presumptions, this study determined the most common symptoms in this patient group by examining the frequency of ear complaints reported in the medical records of patients at the dental outpatient department of Saraswati Institute of Medical Sciences and ENT outpatient department at the Subharti Medical College, Uttar Pradesh.

Material & Methods

A total of 70 clinical records that were regularly used for patients treated over a two-year period were first chosen. Identification, clinical, medical, and dental history, physical and clinical examinations, masticatory and posterior head muscle assessments, temporomandibular joint functional testing, and occlusal examinations are all included in these records. Gender (male and female), age (under 20, between 21 and 30, between 31 and 40, between 41 and 50, and 51 or

older), and the existence of the otological complaints in question that the patient reported to the dentist in charge of patient care were the factors that were examined. Tinnitus, otitis media, deafness, light-headedness, ear fullness, and unbalance were associated symptoms.

SPSS (IBM Statistic 20.0) was used to arrange and statistically analyze the data gathered for this investigation. First, descriptive analysis (variable frequency, central tendency, and dispersion measures) were performed. Tinnitus, deafness, otitis media, dizziness, ear fullness, imbalance, and the number of symptoms were categorized (up to one symptom present and more than one symptom present) and the relationship between age and these symptoms was assessed. The Mann-Whitney test was used to compare the symptoms of tinnitus, hearing loss, dizziness, ear fullness, imbalance, and the number of symptoms (up to one symptom present and more than one symptom present) with age. Five percent was the significance level.

Results

With a ratio of 78.54% to 21.45%, respectively, the observed results show that there are more female patients than male patients. In terms of age groupings, the 41–50 year old group had the highest prevalence of otological symptoms (37%) and was followed by the 51–60 year old group (32%). Regardless of sex or age, the results showed that 87% of people have otological symptoms, which include tinnitus, deafness, dizziness, ear fullness, and imbalance. Tinnitus was the most common symptom, appearing in 42% of all recordings, followed by ear fullness (39%), when we just looked at the existence of symptoms. As indicated in Table 1, the age distribution difference between the groups was statistically significant for the reporting of ear fullness, tinnitus, and the number of dichotomized otological symptoms.

Table 1: Distribution of individuals per variables for tinnitus, deafness, dizziness, ear fullness, imbalance, number of symptoms dichotomized, and age (N = 70)

Variables	Frequency (%)	Age (Mean ± Median)	P Value
Otitis media			
Present	9 (14%)	40.65 ±38.5	0.047
Absent	61 (86%)	35.29±35.4	
Tinnitus			
Present	32 (46%)	40.95 ±38.7	<0.001
Absent	38 (54%)	35.39±34.5	
Deafness			
Present	12 (17.5%)	41.92±39.4	0.001
Absent	58 (82.5%)	37.1±36.2	
Dizziness			
Present	21 (30.5%)	39.44 ±35.7	0.094
Absent	49 (69.5%)	37.29±35.3	
Ear Fullness			
Present	27 (38.4%)	37.59±36.4	0.74
Absent	43 (61.6%)	38.16±35.6	

Imbalance			
Present	11 (14.8%)	40.54±38.43	0.056
Absent	59 (85.2%)	37.49±36.1	
Number of Symptoms			
Up to 1 symptom	40 (57.7%)	36.26±34.5	0.001
> 1 symptom	30 (42.3%)	42.1±36.9	

Table 2 indicates that there were significant ($p < 0.05$) correlations between the symptoms of dizziness and tinnitus and gender.

Table 2: Distribution of otological symptoms in accordance with gender (n =70)

Characters	Tinnitus		Deafness		Dizziness		Fullness		Imbalance		Otitis media	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Female	28	27	10	45	18	37	22	33	9	46	7	47
Male	5	10	2	13	3	12	5	10	2	13	2	14
P value	0.00168		0.1739		0.0205		0.2141		0.7204		0.8251	

Discussion

The relationship between otological symptoms and TMD has been explained by a number of theories, but no single explanation has been offered as of yet. Wright outlines Costen research hypotheses that suggest TMD may result in otological symptoms by restricting the Eustachian tube, damaging auriculotemporal nerves, or causing an incorrect intratympanic pressure adjustment. According to a different explanation, the otological symptoms may result from the masticatory muscles' hyperactivity generating a secondary reflex contraction of the soft palate's tensor muscle, which would impair the Eustachian tube's function.

Other writers think that the connection between TMD and otological symptoms may be due to the entry points of the middle and inner ear, which receive trigeminal nerve impulses and sympathetic nerves from the middle ear through the tympanic plexus. There may be an anatomical basis for a correlation between TMD and otological symptoms, according to cadaveric dissections of the middle ear and TMJ. The petrotympanic fissure connects the sphenomandibular ligament to the jaw and palate in 68% of the samples, while the middle ear connects to the hammer in 8% of the cases. According to this view, the aforementioned mechanisms might serve as the catalyst for otological symptoms. Despite the fact that numerous explanations have been proposed, no agreement has been reached. There may be an anatomical basis for a correlation between TMD and otological symptoms, according to cadaveric dissections of the middle ear and TMJ. The petrotympanic fissure connects the sphenomandibular ligament to the jaw and palate in 68% of the samples, while the middle ear connects to the hammer in 8% of the cases.

Tinnitus, ear fullness, ear discomfort, hearing loss, vertigo, and hyperacusis are otological symptoms that patients with temporomandibular disorders

may have in addition to a variety of symptoms related to the temporomandibular joints, masticatory muscles, and related structures [7,13-16]. This investigation showed that otological symptoms often occur alongside TMD, even when there are no ear-related local reasons, such as infections or other illnesses [11,17].

However, the presence of otological symptoms in patients with painful tenderness in the masticatory muscles is more common and may also cause pain or the aforementioned symptomology with varying auditory symptoms [7,11,18]. The relationship between these diseases is still not fully established, and the type of TMD presented may not be related to the otological symptoms.

According to the data in this study, tinnitus is one of the most common otological symptoms. However, it is known that tinnitus can be caused by a variety of conditions, including joint and muscle issues, and that the causes are not just confined to the ear. In addition to being a cause, these factors can also modulate tinnitus by pressure on the head and neck or jaw movements, and therapy can help reduce or even eliminate symptoms. Tinnitus can have multiple causes in a single person, making diagnosis challenging and necessitating a thorough, multidisciplinary assessment of the patient in order to make the right diagnosis [15].

Numerous writers have investigated this pathology in order to ascertain the relationship between otological symptoms and TMD, concentrating on the joint, muscle, or both. The findings differ depending on the methods used. Variations for the presence of tinnitus concomitantly with TMD was from 20% to 76%; otalgia from 10.8% to 88%; ear fullness from 20% to 90%; vertigo and/or dizziness from 10% to 63%; hypoacusis from 8% to 64%; and finally hyperacusis from 26% to 80%. 87% of the participants in this study had otological symptoms, and 42% of them had tinnitus. There is no proof that otological symptoms and TMD are

related, despite the large range of outcomes; however, more investigation is necessary to determine the precise cause-and-effect link between Variations for the presence of tinnitus concomitantly with TMD was from 20% to 76%; otalgia from 10.8% to 88%; ear fullness from 20% to 90%; vertigo and/or dizziness from 10% to 63%; hypoacusis from 8% to 64%; and finally hyperacusis from 26% to 80%. 87% of the participants in this study had otological symptoms, and 42% of them had tinnitus.

It is not possible to correlate TMD and audiological symptoms with test results since several studies have discovered that, despite the presence of otological symptoms, some audiological tests were within the normal range [7,19-22]. On the other hand, Pekkan et al.'s research showed that the TMD group had a significantly higher trend peak in audiometric tests (audiogram, tympanogram, and Eustachian tube function), as well as the existence of negative pressure in certain patients due to the tympanogram [23].

The tensor tympani muscle contraction may be the cause of this, indicating that people with and without TMD have differing audiologic characteristics. The authors came to the conclusion that there is a connection between TMD and auditory function, however this connection can only be demonstrated if the otological symptoms improve following TMD therapy.

Conventional tympanometry did not reveal any discernible differences between ears in the study by Riga et al. [24].

When compared to the contralateral side of the same patient, the resonance frequency measured by the multiple frequency tympanometry (MFT) test, which measures acoustic impedance, was higher on the ipsilateral side for TMD in 85% of patients. This difference was even more pronounced in patients older than 45.

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Therefore, in contrast to the findings of other research that just employed the latter test to examine acoustic impedance, TMD is an example of a condition in which MFT can identify modest changes in middle ear biomechanics. Consequently, the first concrete indication of an increase in middle ear system rigidity in TMD patients is the considerable rise in resonance frequency values on the ipsilateral side of the TMD, which adds new

details to the pathophysiology of otological symptoms in TMD patients.

Conclusion

Even when there are no local causes in the ears, otological symptoms are frequently present in patients with TMD. Tinnitus, ear pain, ear fullness, vertigo, and hypo- or hyperacusis are the most often reported symptoms.

The findings, which indicate a high frequency of otological symptoms in TMD patients, corroborate a link between TMD and the reported symptoms. The type of TMD in which these symptoms are most common cannot be determined. Additional study is required utilizing suitable and established techniques that can derive more objective procedures to be conducted for differential diagnosis of ear complaints from the outcomes of temporomandibular problems and audiological tests.

Data availability statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/supplementary material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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Conflict of interest: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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